

AGE IS JUST A NUMBER: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF INSTITUTIONALIZED ELDERLY AMID COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The research sought to explore the lived experiences of the institutionalized elderly during this COVID-19 Pandemic. The study utilized a qualitative research design and specifically employed an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. It conducted a semi-structured interview with eight (8) respondents as provided by the institution, however, only six (6) idiographic illustrations have been considered for this research study. The findings of the study have revealed three (3) superordinate themes with three (3) subordinate themes which were classified based on the interconnected themes that were found in the analysis of the transcripts. To conclude, the study revealed that institutionalization amid the pandemic,² has made them think that they are a liability, physically inadequate, and conditionally accepted. This sudden life transition made them feel the pain of not mattering, a longing for freedom, and a high sense of nostalgia. Consequently, despite their negative thoughts and feelings towards institutionalization, they still choose to rise above the challenges by choosing to cope positively. Instead of feeling lonely, they connect with their non-familial relationship, embrace life for what it is, and strengthen their faith in God. As such, the study recommends that it is imperative to create strategic planning to cater to the geriatric population's diverse and progressing needs.

Keywords: *geriatric population, lived experiences, institutionalized elderly, Covid-19 pandemic*

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of aging in the Filipino context is seen through the elders' life experiences, perception of aging, life satisfaction, adaptation, and sense of belongingness (Pagdonsolan, Parel, Parial, Pastor, Peret Ivan & Perez, 2007; Mallari, 2011; Cajayon, et al., 2017; Badana, & Andel, 2018; Salvador, & Alqahtani, 2019). Due to the dignity and maturation that come with age, elderly Filipinos approach this period positively despite a decline in their physical, mental, and other functions (Badana & Andel, 2018). However, a number also face prejudice as they are frequently characterized as liabilities, inept, and helpless (Salvador & Alqahtani, 2019). Statistically speaking, Pambid, Vicente, and Noroña (2021) indicated that at present, the Philippines' aging bracket just like the other countries around the world is numerically growing. Although the country is still considered a young population, as it begins to age, diverse challenges and societal demands concerning elderly support and protection are becoming more visible (Cruz, 2019).

As the Philippines will exceed ten (10) million older adults for the first time at the height of the pandemic, it unswervingly calls for an intensified petition for the elderly's support and health assistance against the risks of the COVID-19 pandemic (POPCOM, 2021). The emerging cases of the COVID-19 outbreak have instigated enduring effects on people across ages in the country (Department of Health, 2021). Globally, recent studies have shown that the most affected individuals by this fatal phenomenon are the elderly, as they are considered the most vulnerable group nowadays (Al-Zahrani, 2020; Vahia, Jeste & Reynolds, 2020; Bundy, H., Lee, H., Sturkey, K. & Caprio, A. 2021; De Pue, Gillebert, Dierckx, Vanderhasselt, Raedt, & Bussche, 2021). The susceptibility of this sector is at stake due to their immunocompromised state, old age, frailty, and comorbidities (Dhama et al., 2020; HelpAge International, 2020; Hubbard, Maier, Hilmer, Naganathan, Etherton- Beer & Rockwood, 2020; Seale et al., 2020). Consequently, the pandemic elicits profound adverse emotional and psychosocial impacts on the geriatric population such as distress, loneliness, anxiety, untold fear, violence, and suffering that can lead to reduced well-being (Chee, 2020; Dubey et al., 2020; Lima et al., 2020; HelpAge International, 2020; Brown, Mossabir, Harrison, Brundle, Smith & Clegg, 2021; Radwan, Radwan & Radwan, 2021). In addition, challenges like activity restrictions, loss of companionship, access to health services, disrupted wellness routines and delayed healthcare visits are also being experienced by older adults during this unprecedented time (Heid, Cartwright, Wilson-Genderson & Pruchno, 2020; Help Age International, 2020; Scott, Yun & Qualls, 2021).

To date, there is a paucity of research studies concerning the Filipino geriatric population as the topic of aging in the Philippines is still young and under-developed

(Villegas, 2014; Badana & Andel, 2018; Carandang, Asis, Shibnuma, Kiriya, Murayama & Jimba, 2019). It was only through the recent establishment of the Institute of Aging by the University of the Philippines- Manila that this area of study has shed light on research interests (Badana & Andel, 2018). Correspondingly, as the Philippines faced the weight of the COVID-19 outbreak, it is being emphasized the need to provide scientific, evidence-based, and personalized care to the geriatric population, and because of that, researchers in this field globally expressed deep concern about the lack of preparedness for emergencies like COVID-19, as well as the public's impression of the virus as a problem affecting the elderly in care institutions (Dhama et al., 2020). This is significant to note since mental health is seen as a critical component of public health in this population, yet few tangible steps have been taken to address this issue (Lebrasseur, et al., 2021). Empirical research, both quantitative and qualitative designs, have shown the importance of addressing the needs of the geriatric community. As older people approach this aging phenomenon, it is crucial to understand their lived experiences, well-being, and coping mechanisms (Duner & Nordstrom, 2005; Lloyd-Williams, et al., 2007; Cooper & Zaman, 2014). Although older Filipinos are rarely institutionalized in their culture, the number of abandoned cases within this group has recently increased (de Guzman, et al., 2012). To espouse, there are studies on elderly institutionalization among Filipinos that highlight the importance and necessity of creating a community that can give way for more connections to achieve a better quality of life and a happier outlook on life (de Guzman, et al., 2012; Runcan, 2012; Mohammad, Dom & Ahmad, 2016). Elderly institutionalization has a negative impact, that's why, to achieve a greater quality of life and a more positive attitude towards life, it's important to emphasize the need for building a community that allows for more engagement to meet the changing needs of our elderly people (Runcan, 2012; Adriano & Dajang, 2013; Mohammad, Dom & Ahmad, 2016). This argument backs up the claim of several researchers that maintaining social support system is very critical as seen in the lived experiences of older adults (de Guzman, et al., 2012; Valdez, Angeles, Pareja-Corpuz & Hernandez, 2013; Dante, 2015; Wijngaarden, et al., 2015; Cajayon, et al., 2017; Salvador & Alqahtani, 2019). However, it is important to note that the lived experiences of the geriatric community vary for each person as each experience is shaped by personal and cultural engagement.

In this regard, the study delved into the lived experiences of the geriatric community, in the context of institutionalized elderly amid the COVID-19 pandemic. The main objective of the study is to explore the lived experiences of the geriatric community, particularly those who are living in an institution during this COVID-19 Pandemic. Specifically, it sought to answer the question, *“What are the lived experiences of the geriatric community amid the COVID-19 pandemic?”* As previously noted, only a few research on the Filipino geriatric population have been undertaken because the area of study when it comes to aging is still developing; this is also true in the case of the country's institutionalized

elderly. The purpose of this study is to uncover their way of meaning-making patterns that have shaped their stay in the institution. In essence, this study is deemed to be significant in policy-making due to the susceptibility of this population to COVID-19. By highlighting the lived experiences of the institutionalized elderly, the findings of the study can help and serve in developing meaningful program intervention efforts as points of action during the pandemic and beyond.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study is to explore the lived experiences of the geriatric community, particularly those who are living in an institution during this COVID-19 Pandemic. Specifically, it sought to answer the question, “*What are the lived experiences of the geriatric community amid the COVID-19 pandemic?*”

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a qualitative research design. Qualitative research explores the quality of relationships, activities, or situations as it emphasizes a very detailed description of what is going on in a specific subject matter (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012). To further understand the experiences of the institutionalized elderly during this pandemic, an interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) was employed. This theoretical approach has allowed the researcher to uncover meaning-making patterns in the elderly’s thoughts, feelings, and actions that have shaped their stay in the institution. In this sense, the basic tenets of *phenomenology*, *hermeneutics*, and *idiography* as the theoretical orientations of IPA were used throughout the research process. To undertake this, the researcher collected and interpreted data through in-depth interviews with the belief that there is a similarity to how each person views and construes their common experiences.

Research Locale

To facilitate, the study was carried out in Bahay Kanlungan- Tahanan ng mga Lolo at Lola in Barangay Maysan, Valenzuela City. Bahay Kanlungan is an institution for elderly people established by The Local Governing Unit (LGU) of Valenzuela City. This institution is being built during the weight of COVID-19 to give shelter to the homeless elderly of the City of Valenzuela. This institution was established in the year 2021 as part of the 152nd birth anniversary of Dr. Pio A. Valenzuela.

Research Participants

Name (Pseudonym)	Gender	Age	Year Admitted	Medical Diagnosis
Abuela	Female	70 y/o	2021	Hypertension Stage I Type II Diabetes
Gramps	Male	62 y/o	2018	Congestive Heart Failure Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Granny Pie	Female	82 y/o	2022	Hypertension Stage I Type II Diabetes
Lala	Female	67 y/o	2020	Hypertension Stage I- controlled
Mémé	Female	63 y/o	2022	Essentially Normal
Nana	Female	70 y/o	2021	Hypertension Stage I
Abuelo	Male	60 y/o	2021	Dyslipidemia
Inkong	Male	74 y/o	2021	Anemia

Table 1 **Biographical Sketch of the Respondents**

The name of participants in the table above was presented using pseudonyms to protect their identity. Initially, the researcher interviewed eight (eight) elderly whose ages range from 60 years old to 82 years old. There are five (5) women and three (3) men. After the initial analysis, the researcher used the transcript of six (6) participants as data saturation has been achieved. Also, to achieve the homogeneity of the participants, the exclusion and inclusion criteria were strictly observed.

Research Instrument

The interview guide was prepared in a semi-structured format. The set of questions in the interview guide was validated by Registered Psychologists and Registered Psychometricians to ensure that the questions measure the constructs that the study intended to measure as well as to guarantee the appropriateness of the language used and its relevance to the study's research statement. In this phenomenological study, the participants were encouraged to expound their answers to the questions that were asked. As the interview guide covered questions related to their lived experiences amid the pandemic, although the instrument was presented in both English and Filipino language,

only the Filipino language was used in communicating the questions to the participants for easier understanding and common use.

Data Gathering Procedure

To facilitate the process, a letter of introduction, letter of intent, and a copy of the interview guide were submitted via email to Ms. Dorothy G. Evangelista, the Chief of Staff on Social Welfare Operations of CSWDO, PDAO, and OSCA. After securing permission to conduct a study, the researcher visited Bahay Kanlungan in Maysan, Valenzuela to directly communicate with the administrators and staff of the institution to discuss the flow of the interview, the forms to be signed, and other information needed for the study. Interviews were conducted on three (3) separate days. It was based on the availability of the respondents and the institution. Before the interview starts, the researcher deliberately explained the purpose and scope of the study. Each participant was given a consent form that they signed or put their thumb mark to indicate their approval to participate in the study. Upon evaluation, no additional follow-up/additional interview was deemed necessary. To ensure the validity and credibility of the themes that were discovered, triangulation was utilized. The researcher specifically employed an investigator and member triangulation where she asked the view of the members (respondents) and the opinions of the investigators (professionals). In addition, data saturation has been seriously taken into consideration in the process of analysis and interpretation. Out of the eight (8) participants that have been interviewed, only six (6) idiographic illustrations have been considered for this research study.

RESULTS

Superordinate Themes	Subordinate Themes
<i>Seeing oneself in the current situation</i>	<i>Institutionalization is the best option Accentuation of physical limitation Quest for belongingness</i>
<i>Feelings toward sudden life transition</i>	<i>Anguish state of not mattering Yearn for autonomy and freedom Sense of nostalgia</i>
<i>Combating institutionalization</i>	<i>Seeks happiness and support in the presence of non-family members Learns to be comfortable in the uncomfortable Clings to spirituality and faith in God's intervention</i>

Table 2 **Superordinate Themes and Subordinate Themes of the Study**

Interpretative phenomenological analysis was utilized to examine and interpret the participants' experiences to answer the research question. Testimonies of all six

participants were used to provide explanations for the events that the study looked into. As the data were analyzed using the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), three (3) superordinate themes were identified - (a) *Seeing oneself in the current situation*; (b) *Feelings toward sudden life transition*, and (c) *Combating institutionalization*. These were classified based on the subordinate themes that were found in the analysis of the transcripts. For the superordinate theme – Seeing oneself in the current situation, the subordinate themes are: (a) *Institutionalization is the best option*, (b) *Accentuation of physical limitation*, and (c) *Quest for belongingness*. Next, for the superordinate theme – Feelings toward sudden life transition, the subordinate themes are (a) *Anguish state of not mattering*, (b) *Yearn for autonomy and freedom*, and (c) *Sense of nostalgia*. And lastly, for the superordinate theme – Combating institutionalization, the subordinate themes are: (a) *Seeks happiness and support in the presence of non-family members*, (b) *Learns to be comfortable in the uncomfortable*, and (c) *Clings to spirituality and faith in God’s intervention*.

DISCUSSION

Seeing Oneself in the Current Situation

This superordinate theme talks about what the elderly think about themselves inside the institution and their common thoughts about their current situation.

Institutionalization is the best option. Transcripts revealed that all the participants thought that being institutionalized is the only and last option available for them. Being left alone, with no family members who would be willing to take care of them, and nowhere to go, has left them with no choice but to resort to living in an institution to survive the weight of the pandemic and beyond.

“I’ve been asked to transfer, I have nowhere to go to... I’m ashamed, so I asked the help of my adopted child to pass my application here.” (Abuela)

With a place that they can call now home and refuge, the elderly are so grateful for where they are right now, and no indication of regrets exists.

“I was brought there. I told the Lord, thank you because here I can sleep well, eat, and take a bath, meaning to say, all in all; I am surviving, far from danger. I said, thank you, that’s what they did to me, Ma’am.” (Gramps)

This is related to the study which states that some elderly people think that it is a burden to be taken care of by their significant others despite spending a large portion of their lives taking care of them (White, 2005). In this sense, the elderly people see themselves in a

helpless situation in the face of the pandemic which led them to enter the city-owned facility. The narratives of the elderly pointed out that the best decision that they could do due to their situation is to be admitted to Bahay Kanlungan.

Accentuation of physical limitation. During the interview, each elderly kept on stressing about their present physical limitations. They see themselves as someone who is now physically inadequate to the things they love. They emphasized their experiences regarding the physical difficulties they encountered brought about by their old age.

“...To be honest, my eyes are not that clear... Oh Lord, you know, Ma’am, I don’t know what I look like because there’s no mirror here. So, there were times when my eyebrows were here, and sometimes, some house parents would react on my eyebrows because we are not allowed to have a mirror. Back then, I used to wear eyeglasses; when I was admitted here, they told me that my eyes would be lasered because of catarata, but none happened.” (Abuela)

In addition, while inside the institution, they see themselves as someone who is physically inadequate, which made them think that because of these physical concerns, they can’t socialize with others inside. For instance, daily, some of them would normally be quiet and spend time alone.

“I am just lying in the bed, just quiet primarily because of my eyes; I cannot boast in my words or what, I am just quiet.” (Granny Pie)

Based on the narratives of the elderly, issues about their physical self are found to be one of the primary reasons that influenced their decision to stay in Bahay Kanlungan. Deterioration and impairment in the aspect of physical health status are commonly associated with growing older. Older Filipinos’ health functioning was found to have an impact on their total years of good life (Vicerra, 2022). Although the indicator is not limited to age alone, the prevalence of physical disability could affect the elderly’s way of living and quality of life. Taken from the narratives of the respondents, their physical issues not only limit them from doing the things that they were doing before but also withhold them from socializing with the people around them.

Quest for belongingness. This subordinate theme highlights the thoughts of each elderly based on their need to be accepted. The elderly people are on the journey of finding belongingness before they enter the institution, and it continues even after they are admitted. As they search for belongingness, they think that they need to modify how they behave, different from how they have been before their admission.

“ah to change something, you need to be patient, because before, as a mother, I’m just at home, right? But here, I have seen different attitudes and behaviors, and you need to study and learn from them. In fact, I have learned how to just eat a certain amount. I have learned how to mingle with different types of people and attitudes. That’s it...because you need to, because you are not just there alone, you are with other people, and you are in a different home.” (Abuela)

The elderly people continue to seek a sense of belonging, which has caused them to construct conditions of worth as they stay in the institution. They believe that to feel that they belong inside the institution, they must act in a certain way. This behavior includes changing the way they relate with other people, strict adherence to the rules and regulations, and doing something to help the staff inside the institution. Indirectly, they believe that if they break these behaviors, they will be disliked and rejected by the people around them- the staff and their fellow elders. Feeling unwanted before admission, such acts are manifestations of their quest for belongingness. They search for approval to feel loved, valued, and belong.

Feelings Toward Sudden Life Transition

This superordinate theme talks about how the elderly feel about themselves towards the grand exodus that they have unexpectedly faced. This theme points out the emotion that they have felt upon their admission.

Anguish state of not mattering. This subordinate theme underscores the way they feel about their family as their significant people. By feeling that they do not matter, the elderly expressed their sorrow and aches of feeling unimportant to those whom they regarded significant in their lives.

“I also do not like to stay with them because they have their own family now. Maybe, they also do not like responsibility, because our younger generation nowadays is much different.” (Abuela)

*“Ma’am, that’s how they repay me, they chose to let me go *short pause* and they don’t have any regrets on that. So, I am deeply hurt for what they have done.” (Granny Pie)*

Elderly people must maintain closeness and bond with family members (Chen, et al., 2008). As such, proximity and frequent family contact have an impact on the general well-being and sense of fulfillment in the life of the elderly. This could be the primary reason why the respondents have an anguished state of not mattering. This anguish state manifests in the elderly by feeling like a burden by remaining with their family, by feeling deserted despite good deeds done for their family, and by feeling that their family has

forgotten them. Because of their experiences before admission, feelings of abandonment, insignificance, and unimportance have resulted in feeling such emotions in the course of their sudden life transition.

Yearning for autonomy and freedom. This subordinate theme emphasizes their feelings of longing for freedom and autonomy while inside the institution. The elderly expressed their desire to be independent and in control of their life, just as they had been before the pandemic and before they were admitted to the institution.

“What I would like to go back to is the time when I was still free, unlike today when there’s a pandemic. So, sometimes I like to ask when will this situation get better so we can live normally like before. That’s it, Ma’am, that’s what I like, to go back when freedom is still in our hands.” (Abuela)

In addition, being confined inside, with institutional rules and pandemic protocols to obey, the situation made them feel that they wished to move freely not just inside the institution realms but also outside to pursue something they were doing in the past.

“It is better before because we can go to different places that we like, you can freely walk, freely move inside the jeep... here, we are confined inside, we can’t go out.” (Lala)

Two of the significant challenges that institutionalized elderly must face are losing independence and sharing space, both of which can trigger depressive symptoms and erode one's sense of self and well-being (Melendez-Moral, et al., 2014). Narratives of the elderly bring to light the comparison between their lives before and after they were admitted to the institution. Bound by the institutional routines and rules on top of the pandemic protocols, the elders feel restricted, regulated, and limited. This sudden life transition made them yearn for liberty to go outside the four walls of their room and the facility. Such longing is also expressed with the desire to leave the facility to pursue a dream, get a job, and help others as well. As a result, they long for freedom and independence—not just in terms of matters of institutions, but also in terms of having control over their lives just like before.

Sense of nostalgia. This subordinate theme draws attention to how the elderly feel about their past. The elderly reminisced about the things they love to do and the memories they had before with their significant others.

“Before, I can see them, but now I cannot. How can I see them if both of us are far from each other. I’m in a far place, how can I see them?” (Mémé)

The participants also shared a memory that they love doing with the significant people around them like singing with their choir mates, chatting with their neighbors, and bonding with their workmates.

“When I am still working because I felt like my life was better then. I have many friends there.” (Gramps)

Rooted in their feelings toward their sudden life transition, the elderly talk about their feelings of longing for the past. Loneliness is one of the many emotions that can elicit especially for institutionalized elderly who lack family support. The narratives of the respondents highlight how they miss their past- the people in it and their former way of living. The grand exodus that they have faced unexpectedly has made them feel their longing for the good old times spent with loved ones.

Combating Institutionalization

This superordinate theme explores how the elderly handle their stay in the institution through their coping mechanism. The elderly conveyed their personal way of coping with their present condition.

Seeks happiness and support in the presence of non-family members. This subordinate theme denotes a coping mechanism for the elderly inside the institution. Because of feeling insignificant and being abandoned by their family and loved ones, they consider the company and presence of their non-familial relationship as a source of happiness and support that they need while inside the institution.

“Fellowships like this make us happy, just two weeks ago, the senior citizens of Valenzuela visited us, and they organized a program. It makes us so happy because, through that, we can forget all our sorrows and pain... Like thus, I feel happy when I am being interviewed, at least I have someone I can express my feelings to.” (Abuela)

“Yes, it’s happy, but of course when you remember your siblings, sometimes, you get sad; but when my friends are here, the others, I’m happy. If you know how to get along, it’ll be okay.” (Nana)

“Yes, sometimes there are people who visit for prayer meeting, there are also other institutions for us. We were happy on those days.” (Gramps)

In the case of the respondents, transcripts revealed that as a way of coping with their stay in the institution, they generally look at their non-familial relationship as an alternative source of happiness and support. They find themselves happy whenever people are

visiting them like students, social workers, fellow-senior citizens, and people from different religious groups. With that, it can be true that the happiness decline among the elderly can be halted by having a sufficient social support system and connection with others⁴⁹. Thus, this theme conveys that doing that, helped the elderly to keep going despite the adverse thoughts and feelings that they have experienced.

Learns to be comfortable in the uncomfortable. This subordinate theme highlights how the elderly face their present life in the institution. The elderly talk about the ways they embrace discomfort and unfamiliarity by learning to be comfortable with the uncomfortable.

“It’s like, at first, it’s kind of hard, I find it hard... but as the days go by, I like it here. I like mingling with them. At first of course, I wondered, then, I got used to it; since I don’t the people at first, I cooperated and adjusted so, as days passed by, it’s okay.” (Nana)

Interviews of the participants have shown how the elderly deal with institutional routines. It showed how the elderly are starting to slowly embrace the new way of life as their coping mechanism for combating institutionalization. Contrary to what they usually come across in the past, life inside the institution entails learning to be comfortable in the uncomfortable. It allowed them to go out of what they considered their personal norm. Each narrative describes the way they embrace their new life and find meaning in learning to embrace their new reality, their new life as institutionalized elderly.

Clings to spirituality and faith in God’s intervention. This subordinate theme presents another coping strategy used by elderly people living in institutions. The elderly demonstrated their faith in God by praying and believing in Him to help them get by while living at the facility.

“First of all is prayer...number 1 for me is prayer. This is all we need. Even though you can’t see Him, you need to talk to Him. When you do it, everything is lighter... and your feelings are truly lightened. I leave it to You (referring to God, help me, I can’t ask for more in God,” (Nana)

“I am enduring everything, Ma’am. May God be with me. Calling Him... calling upon Him to help me- to grant all the things I desire, to taste and see a new life.” (Granny Pie)

The pandemic protocols might have prevented the elderly from participating in religious events and practices but their faith in God remained unaffected. Despite their uttered and unuttered thoughts and feelings, the participants are combating institutionalization

amid the pandemic by clinging to spirituality and faith in God's intervention. Religion and spiritual coping strategies have a significant impact on the participants in general when it comes to dealing with the issues associated with aging³⁶. Narratives of the participants have stressed that prayer is their primary weapon in this battle and that God will see them through this hardship. Religiously active people frequently recover from hardship because faith can offer social support and foster optimism in the face of vulnerability (Brown & Tierney, 2009). As such, as a coping strategy, religion is likely to be remarkably significant for the elderly in terms of their subjective well-being.

Conclusions

This study investigated the lived experiences of the geriatric community amid the COVID-19 pandemic. It revealed that the way the elderly think, feel, and act plays a vital role in their stay at the institution. Filipino culture rarely institutionalizes the elderly because people always expect the family to provide innumerable sacrifices and sustain the idea of self-sacrificing (Pambid, Vicente & Noroña, 2021). Just like in the case of the participants of the study, for them, institutionalization is not certainly a goal, but they came up with the thought of admitting themselves to the institution to be able to survive the weight of the pandemic.

This study is congruent with Medeiros et al. (2020) who concurred that institutionalization has a detrimental impact on the lives of the elderly. The fact that they are struggling to survive the COVID-19 pandemic makes their predicament more complex. What is common about the participants of the study is that all of them experienced prejudice due to their old age. The narratives have shown that they are being referred to as liabilities, useless, and hopeless (Salvador and Alqahtani, 2019). This can result in negative views and feelings about themselves. For the participants of the study, institutionalization amid the pandemic has made them think that they are a liability, physically inadequate, and conditionally accepted. This sudden life transition made them feel the pain of not mattering, a longing for freedom, and a high sense of nostalgia. Consequently, despite their negative thoughts and feelings towards institutionalization, they still choose to rise above the challenges by choosing to cope positively. Instead of feeling lonely, they connect with their non-familial relationship, embrace life for what it is, and strengthen their faith in God.

It is crucial to take into mind that the geriatric community is not only particularly vulnerable to the morbidity of the COVID-19 pandemic but also to the effect of institutionalization. It is also imperative to note that the regimented lifestyle of institutionalized elderly, who lack independence and privacy, also adds to their negative

effects (Soumya, Anagha & Amulya, 2020). Furthermore, it is hugely important to address not just the physiological needs of the elderly but their emotional needs as well because as people get older, they become more socially isolated, and lose their social networks. As such, this study would like to emphasize that when a sense of belonging is improved, there is a possibility that reasons for life can also be improved.

Aging has social, economic, and psychological effects that affect not only the aged people but also the whole society at large. As institutionalization posed a detrimental impact on the lives of the elderly, their predicament has become more complex due to the challenges that were brought to them by the fatal phenomenon called the COVID-19 pandemic. Since geropsychology, as one of the branches of psychology is not being given much attention, the devastating effects of the COVID-19 phenomenon may signal a new epoch in the provision of care and welfare of our elderly. With that, having people, who are in the field of psychology and mental health can be a valuable ally in navigating all the changes brought on by this process of human development.

Recommendations

By examining the lived experiences of the geriatric community, creating intervention programs specially designed for them can be a powerful point of action. As such, it is imperative to create strategic planning to cater to the geriatric population's diverse and progressing needs. The social and medical requirements of the elderly are beyond the capacity of the country. As such, the Administrators of the Institutions should work hand in hand with the local government unit in establishing and building elderly nursing homes among their constituents.

As the geriatric community is not only specifically vulnerable to the adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic but also to the impact of institutionalization, the workforce – nurses, caregivers, guidance counselors, and psychologists must have adequate training to deal with the elderly as they require a complex array of care and management.

To combat loneliness and isolation, a sense of belongingness among the elderly should also be given huge importance as it will increase their reasons to continue living. This can be done through support programs for the elderly. Help them to connect with the people around them and the visitors outside the facility.

As the aging bracket in the country is increasing, the researchers are hereby encouraged to conduct more studies on the Filipino elderly to shed light on the needs and challenges of this population. Psychology practitioners are also encouraged to advocate for the geriatric community as valuable members of society.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The protection of the respondents' rights, dignities, and privacies is a sacred obligation of a qualitative researcher most especially in the context of IPA (Alase, 2017). To facilitate the study, the researcher sought an Ethical Clearance Certificate from the Graduate School of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines. This certificate has allowed the researcher to conduct the data gathering. The researcher has sought approval from the Office of Social Welfare Operations of CSWDO, PDAO, and OSCA. All participants have freely and voluntarily given their consent to participate in the study after a thorough explanation of the purpose of the study. Likewise, audio recordings were done upon the participants' consent. The staff-in-charge in the institution was asked to countersign the form as a witness. During the interview, the participants' safety and comfort were assured by the researcher and institution personnel. Also, it is important to note that the researcher has prepared a distress protocol that was observed and followed throughout the interview. This distress protocol indicates that if the participant has shown symptoms of distress and cannot continue the interview anymore, an on-call Psychologist will be asked to speak with the participant. To report, during the interview with the participants, the researcher did not encounter any distressed participants.

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